

D7.6

Communication Tools – Version II

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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03	01/03/2024	Céline Lefort – ERTICO	Clean version with changes incorporated
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Table of Contents

- Contributors..... 2
- Quality Control..... 2
- Version History 2
- Legal Disclaimer 3
- Table of Contents 4**
- List of Figures 6
- List of abbreviations and acronyms..... 7
- Executive Summary..... 8**
- 1. Introduction 9**
 - 1.1. Project introduction 9
 - 1.2. Purpose of the deliverable 9
 - 1.3. Intended audience..... 9
- 2. Digital Media 11**
 - 2.1. PoDIUM website..... 11
 - 2.1.1. Structure and content 11
 - 2.1.1.1. Home page..... 11
 - 2.1.1.2. About 12
 - 2.1.1.3. Living Labs..... 13
 - 2.1.1.4. News & Events..... 13
 - 2.1.1.5. Library..... 14
 - 2.1.1.6. Contact 14
 - 2.1.2. Monitoring 15
 - 2.2. Social media channels 16
 - 2.2.1. LinkedIn 16
 - 2.2.2. X/Twitter 17
 - 2.3. Zenodo Community 18
 - 2.4. News articles 19
 - 2.5. Newsletter 20
 - 2.6. Press releases 21
 - 2.7. Videos and YouTube channel 21
 - 2.8. Webinars 23
 - 2.9. Infographic..... 23
 - 2.10. Ad hoc digital promotional material 24

2.11. Internal communication tools	25
3. Printed Media	26
3.1. Roll-up banner	26
3.2. Flyers	27
3.3. Posters	28
3.4. Ad hoc printed promotional material	29
4. Conclusion.....	30
5. Annex.....	31

List of Figures

Figure 1: PoDIUM website – Home page (top part).....	11
Figure 2: PoDIUM website – Home page (bottom part)	12
Figure 3: PoDIUM website – About page (top part).....	12
Figure 4: PoDIUM website – About page (consortium section).....	13
Figure 5: PoDIUM website – Living Labs page.....	13
Figure 6: PoDIUM website – Events section.....	14
Figure 7: PoDIUM website – Library page (promotional materials section).....	14
Figure 8: PoDIUM website – Contact page.....	15
Figure 9: Screenshot of the number of visitors on the PoDIUM website since its launch.....	15
Figure 10: Screenshot of the PoDIUM LinkedIn page	16
Figure 11: PoDIUM’s LinkedIn posts Organic Impressions Feb 2023 – Feb 2024	17
Figure 12: Screenshot of the PoDIUM Twitter account	18
Figure 13: PoDIUM’s Zenodo Community.....	19
Figure 14: Hero image of the article on the German Living Lab	20
Figure 15: Screenshots of the second PoDIUM newsletter	21
Figure 16: PoDIUM Introductory Video (Full Name).....	22
Figure 17: PoDIUM Introductory Video (Use Case 1, German Living Lab)	22
Figure 18: PoDIUM Introductory Video (Consortium Members).....	23
Figure 19: Infographic of the PoDIUM high-level platform architecture	24
Figure 20: Banner advertising the first PoDIUM webinar	24
Figure 21: PoDIUM roll-up banner	26
Figure 22: PoDIUM roll-up banner displayed at the EUCAD 2023	27
Figure 23: PoDIUM leaflet	28
Figure 24: PoDIUM poster	29
Figure 25: PoDIUM LinkedIn Content Engagement (Feb 23 – Feb 24).....	31
Figure 26: Continued.....	32

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
UC	Use Case
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the updated version of *D7.3 Communication tools*. It presents an update of the various communication tools of the PoDIUM project, their main features and how they are used to support the PoDIUM communication strategy and plan and maximise the impact of the project's communication. It also provides an overview of their status and achievements. The tools developed as part of the project cover both electronic and printed media. This ensures that the right type of communication materials is used depending on the communication or dissemination activity that is conducted. The tools at the disposal of the consortium include a website, an X/Twitter and LinkedIn page, a biannual newsletter, videos, an infographic, a roll-up banner, flyers, and posters. All communication materials are in line with the project's brand identity to ensure the cohesive representation of PoDIUM.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows:

- Chapter 1 (Introduction) provides a brief description of PoDIUM, explains the purpose of this deliverable and gives information on the target audience of the document.
- Chapter 2 (Digital Media) presents the digital media developed as part of the project. The digital media include the PoDIUM website, social media channels, newsletter, videos, an infographic, and internal communication tools at the disposal of the consortium.
- Chapter 3 (Printed Media) outlines the printed media of the project, which include the roll-up banner, flyers, and posters.
- Chapter 4 (Conclusions) provides concluding remarks.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM tackles all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions is pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advance data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of Deliverable D7.6 *Communication tools – Version II* is to present the updated development of the different tools developed as part of the project to support its communication strategy and ensure that the materials that are produced are in line with the project's brand identity. This document describes both the digital and printed materials that are developed to promote PoDIUM.

This document is complementary to Deliverable D7.1 *Brand identity and guidelines*, Deliverable D7.4 *Dissemination Plan* and Deliverable D7.5 *Communication strategy and plan – Version II*. Deliverable D7.1 presents the brand identity and guidelines related to the PoDIUM brand to ensure its consistent representation in all communication and dissemination activities carried out by the consortium partners. It also describes the different templates that have been developed, including a Word template for deliverables and a PowerPoint template for presentations. Deliverable D7.4 details the dissemination strategy and plan of PoDIUM. All dissemination activities are supported by the tools and promoted using the channels described in this document. Deliverable D7.5 presents the updated communication strategy of the PoDIUM project and provides details about the target audiences, stakeholders, and key messages the project focuses on for its communication efforts.

1.3. Intended audience

This is a public document. For the consortium of PoDIUM, this document is intended to serve as a reference document explaining the structure of the website and listing the different tools supporting

the communication and dissemination activities of the project. For external stakeholders and the broader public, this deliverable helps create an understanding of the different tools and promotional materials of the project and how to access them.

2. Digital Media

2.1. PoDIUM website

The PoDIUM website can be accessed through the following link: www.podium-project.eu. It acts as a one-stop place containing the most important information about the project, presented in a clear and accessible way to the public. The website has been launched at M5 (February 2023) and has been developed by ERTICO, who keeps it continuously updated to make sure the information it contains remains correct and relevant.

2.1.1. Structure and content

The PoDIUM website is structured as follows below. The menu of the website listing the different pages remains visible on top of all the pages. Each page also includes a footer containing the PoDIUM logo, links to social media channels, EU funding acknowledgment, and the cookies policy and privacy policy.

2.1.1.1. Home page

- <https://podium-project.eu/>
- Short description of PoDIUM with link to About page
- Key facts and figures about the project
- Short overview of the project’s objectives
- Latest news: this section shows the last 3 news articles that were published
- Form to sign up for the PoDIUM newsletter
- Module with the latest tweets from the PoDIUM X/Twitter account

Figure 1: PoDIUM website – Home page (top part)

Figure 2: PoDIUM website – Home page (bottom part)

2.1.1.2. About

- <https://podium-project.eu/about/>
- Longer, more detailed description of the project
- Key facts and figures about the project
- List of the objectives of the project
- Logos of the consortium partners, with a short description and link to their websites in a pop-in window

Figure 3: PoDIUM website – About page (top part)

Figure 4: PoDIUM website – About page (consortium section)

2.1.1.3. Living Labs

- <https://podium-project.eu/living-labs/>
- Map of Europe showing the location of the Living Labs and the use cases
- Description of the use cases and of the Living Labs
- Detailed description of the use cases for each Living Lab, as well as logos of the partners involved, on separate sub-pages. These sub-pages will be updated with more information as soon as available, such as videos and photos of the demonstrations, interviews and/or articles on the progress of the Living Labs activities.

Figure 5: PoDIUM website – Living Labs page

2.1.1.4. News & Events

- <https://podium-project.eu/news-events/>
- List of the last three news articles that were published, with a link to see all news articles
- List of three upcoming events, with a link to see all events, including previous events

- Form to sign up for the PoDIUM newsletter

Figure 6: PoDIUM website – Events section

2.1.1.5. Library

- <https://podium-project.eu/library/>
- List of public deliverables, publications, media (photos or videos developed as part of the project), promotional materials (such as leaflet, logo package, etc.), and articles mentioning the project

Figure 7: PoDIUM website – Library page (promotional materials section)

2.1.1.6. Contact

- <https://podium-project.eu/contact/>
- Contact form and email addresses of the Project Coordinator and the Communication Manager

- Form to sign up for the PoDIUM newsletter

Figure 8: PoDIUM website – Contact page

2.1.2. Monitoring

The website is monitored using Google Analytics 4. This provides statistics on the usage of the website, the audience accessing the website, and the most visited pages, among other metrics. This helps ensure that the website performs in line with the KPIs set in Deliverable D7.5 *Communication strategy and plan*, analyse strong points and weaknesses of the website and take appropriate measures if needed.

The KPI for the number of visitors per month of the website is at least 50 visitors in Year 1, at least 100 visitors in Year 2, and at least 150 visitors in Year 3. As of mid-March 2024, the website counted an average of 185 visitors per month, already exceeding the KPI set for the last year of the project.

Figure 9: Screenshot of the number of visitors on the PoDIUM website since its launch

2.2. Social media channels

2.2.1. LinkedIn

A LinkedIn company page, [PoDIUM Project](#), has been created for the project by ICCS, who manages the page. All major updates, announcements, developments, and any other relevant and interesting content from the partners’ and other stakeholders’ channels are shared on this page on a regular basis. All PoDIUM partners should follow the page and interact with its contents to help promote it to their own networks.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have also been set for the number of followers of the LinkedIn page of the project, which is set to 75 followers in Year 1, 100 followers in Year 2, and 150 followers in Year 3. The LinkedIn page is performing very well and counted 248 followers in mid-March 2024 (M18), which largely exceeds the KPIs set.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the PoDIUM LinkedIn page

On average, PoDIUM shares five posts per month on LinkedIn, reaching 16.925 impressions¹ per year, as seen in Figure 11 below.

¹ LinkedIn Impressions are the number of times a post, video, update, or article appears is displayed or seen by a user on their LinkedIn page.

Figure 11: PoDIUM’s LinkedIn posts Organic Impressions Feb 2023 – Feb 2024

The posts that have been performing best in terms of impressions, links and engagement are related to the project’s General Assemblies, the publication of the newsletter, as well as the news articles that are prepared by the Consortium and posted on the website, e.g. the article related to PoDIUM’s high-level architecture platform and the description of the project’s three Living labs. A detailed analysis of the latest 20 LinkedIn posts can be found in Annex 1.

2.2.2. X/Twitter

An X/Twitter account has also been developed for the project, [@PoDIUM_EU](#). This account shares news regarding the project’s activities and achievements and interacts with relevant stakeholders in real time. Consortium partners follow the X/Twitter account and are constantly encouraged to tag the project’s account and use the hashtag #PoDIUM_EU when posting about the project. The hashtag and tags help monitor posts and increase awareness of the project. The project’s X/Twitter account has been created and is managed by ICCS. The number of followers of the PoDIUM Twitter account in mid-March 2024 was 87 followers.

The KPI set for the number of PoDIUM hashtags (#PoDIUM_EU) used on X/Twitter set in Deliverable D7.5 *Communication strategy and plan* is 60 hashtags in Year 1, 100 hashtags in Year 2, and 140 hashtags in Year 3. On average, PoDIUM shares four posts per month, reaching 82 followers by M18. As of mid-February 2024, 57 posts, original and reposts, have been shared on PoDIUM’s X/Twitter account and an overall of 47 posts featured the hashtag #PoDIUM_EU, which is slightly below the KPI set for Year 1. This can be explained by the recent uncertainty around the management of the platform, which leads to X/Twitter getting less overall engagement as major companies decided to leave the platform. The upcoming developments expected in the project’s Living Labs as well as ramped up participation in events should lead to more opportunities for posts on X/Twitter in the future.

Figure 12: Screenshot of the PoDIUM Twitter account

2.3. Zenodo Community

A specific aim of the EU’s Open Science policy is to require all publicly funded research data to be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and open by default. This is even a contractual requirement for all Horizon Europe projects and beneficiaries. Adhering to this commitment, PoDIUM has created a Zenodo Community in M05 to make freely available and under open access status all public deliverables, scientific publications and publicly available results. The [PoDIUM Zenodo Community](#) (Figure 13) is regularly updated to ensure that all available research outputs are in one place and open to everyone.

Figure 13: PoDIUM’s Zenodo Community

2.4. News articles

News articles on the PoDIUM website are an important aspect of the communication efforts of the project. The [news section](#) of the website is constantly kept updated with interesting content related to the project, highlighting participation in international events and project developments. Events organised by the project are also advertised through news items, such as the first PoDIUM webinar which was the focus of several news items including an [announcement](#) and a [summary article](#) of the discussions, which also provides links to the recording of the webinar and the presentations given. A subpage dedicated to the PoDIUM webinars will be created later to compile under one place all details related to them.

Particular attention was given to introducing the partners’ work in the project while providing insight into specific aspects of the project. An [article on ICCS](#), the project coordinator, focuses on the unique aspects of PoDIUM and its expected impacts, while another [article on AustriaTech](#) provides more information on data management.

Three articles presenting the project’s Living Labs in [Germany](#), [Spain](#), and [Italy](#) were also published on the website as part a series called ‘Inside PoDIUM’s Living Labs’. These articles provide detailed information on the use cases that will be demonstrated there, including information on the location, expected impact. The roles of the different project partners involved in the Living Labs activities is also outlined in these articles.

Figure 14: Hero image of the article on the German Living Lab

As of mid-February 2024, 26 news items have been published on the PoDIUM website.

2.5. Newsletter

A newsletter has been developed and sent out twice a year to inform all interested stakeholders of the latest news and developments of the project. To comply with GDPR, the newsletter is only sent out to a mailing list of subscribers who have actively signed up to receive it, using the subscription form available on the PoDIUM website. The subscriber database has been set up using MailChimp and counted 40 subscribers in mid-March 2024.

The newsletter features the latest project news, upcoming events, milestones and achievements. It is promoted on the PoDIUM website and social media channels, as well as on the Zenodo Community of the project. The consortium partners should circulate the newsletter through their own channels to increase its outreach. All partners are invited to contribute to the content of the newsletter.

The first newsletter was sent out on 6 July 2023. It reached 27 recipients, with an open rate of 59,3% and a click rate of 11,1%. A second newsletter was sent out on 19 December 2023 to 35 recipients. The open rate was 42,9% and the click rate 17,1%. The project plans to issue 8 newsletters in total.

Figure 15: Screenshots of the second PoDIUM newsletter

2.6. Press releases

Press releases to highlight noteworthy project announcement and achievements will be created throughout the lifecycle of the project. A first press release was created after the official kick-off of the project and was shared with partners to be translated and distributed in local media.

During the second half of the project, joint press releases dedicated to the trials and the demonstrations of the partners involved in each Living Lab will be created to help increase visibility of their activities and attract attention from the media, industry stakeholders, and the public, engaging with a broader audience and enhancing the project’s reputation and impact.

Other press releases will be prepared for any other major project event or milestone, such as the PoDIUM final event.

2.7. Videos and YouTube channel

A YouTube channel for the project will be created to host PoDIUM’s videos, which aim to promote the project and raise awareness of PoDIUM, taking into account the intended audience. The videos will also be published on the PoDIUM website and will be shared on the social media channels of PoDIUM and the partners. The videos will also be published on the ERTICO YouTube channel on a separate playlist dedicated to PoDIUM.

The project’s first video was created in M17, serving as an introduction to the project. This is an animated video focusing on:

- PoDIUM’s objectives
- PDI components
- The project’s three Living Labs and five Use Cases
- PoDIUM’s high-level platform architecture

- The consortium
- Funding, duration and contact information

Certain parts of the video that describe the project’s Living Labs and Use Cases will also be used separately to support communication and dissemination activities when necessary and applicable. They will also provide a basis to build upon the three project live-action videos that will focus on explaining and promoting the work done in the different Living Labs. A video compiling the project’s demonstration activities and showcasing the project’s main challenges and results will be created towards the end of the project. Overall, the PoDIUM project will create at least five videos during its lifecycle, as set out in the KPIs in Deliverable D7.2.

Figure 16: PoDIUM Introductory Video (Full Name)

Figure 17: PoDIUM Introductory Video (Use Case 1, German Living Lab)

Figure 18: PoDIUM Introductory Video (Consortium Members)

2.8. Webinars

Webinars are organised by the consortium to present important milestones and the raise awareness of the objectives and activities in the different Living Labs. The consortium will also seek opportunities to organise or participate in webinars with C-Roads and other EC Projects.

2.9. Infographic

A professional infographic image of the PoDIUM high-level platform architecture has been produced at the end of Year 1 to facilitate the communication of this important technical aspect of the project, which serves as the basis for the developments in the PoDIUM Living Lab. The image illustrates in a clear way the different components of the platform architecture and how they relate.

The image was promoted on the project website in a [news item](#), which was also shared on the project’s social media channels. The image has been used in presentations of the project at various events and will continue to be used for diverse communication and dissemination purposes by consortium members.

High-level platform architecture

Figure 19: Infographic of the PoDIUM high-level platform architecture

2.10. Ad hoc digital promotional material

Banners and other images will be created for specific purposes on an ad hoc basis. For instance, a banner was created to promote the first PoDIUM webinar (Figure 20). Other similar images will be produced for other project events or based on specific needs.

Figure 20: Banner advertising the first PoDIUM webinar

2.11. Internal communication tools

Different internal communication tools are also at the disposal of the consortium. The PoDIUM brand identity and guidelines, including the different versions of the logo, and the deliverable and PowerPoint templates are described in detail in Deliverable D7.1 *Brand identity and guidelines* and help ensure that the PoDIUM brand is used consistently by the consortium in all their communication and dissemination activities.

3. Printed Media

3.1. Roll-up banner

A set of roll-up banners (Figure 21) has been developed to provide key information on PoDIUM, such as the project’s objectives, and links to its website and social media, presented in a visual and attractive way. The roll-up banner has been used to promote the project to the wider audience at various events and exhibitions, whether organised as part of the project or external events (see for instance Figure 22).

Figure 21: PoDIUM roll-up banner

Figure 22: PoDIUM roll-up banner displayed at the EUCAD 2023

3.2. Flyers

A flagship flyer (Figure 23) has been developed at M6 (March 2023) of the project. The flyer presents the project in greater detail and includes the objectives of PoDIUM, information on the use cases and the Living Labs, and the consortium partners. In addition to the flagship flyer, technical leaflets may also be developed to provide more information on technical aspects of the project, such as the use cases and PDI technologies.

The leaflet will be updated in Year 2 and will focus on the Living Labs, providing more details on the Use Cases that will be demonstrated. The final update of the leaflet, during Year 3, will summarise the main takeaways and results from PoDIUM.

The leaflet has been distributed at various external events and conferences and at PoDIUM meetings. A digital version of the leaflet is also publicly available to download on the project’s website.

At the end of Year 1, about 40 leaflets had been distributed at events, which is below the KPI set of at least 100. As the project will have more opportunities to disseminate its technical results at events in the second and last phase of the project, the KPIs set in D7.5 *Communication strategy and plan* are expected to be reached.

PoDIUM
Accelerating the implementation of CCAM technology

OBJECTIVES

PoDIUM will facilitate higher levels of automation by:

- assessing connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs;
- specifying the availability and performance of connectivity and cooperation;
- defining methods to ensure the quality and trust of external data;
- advancing key innovative technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure;
- defining a flexible platform architecture following a "multi-connectivity approach";
- examining feasibility and sustainability concepts in real traffic conditions;
- creating new business models and market services;
- promoting the project developments to standardisation bodies and policymakers;
- increasing road safety mainly for Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) and reducing automotive carbon footprint.

PODIUM is an Horizon Europe Project that will identify and assess the connectivity and cooperation enablers to reach higher levels of automation and advance important Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) technologies through a multi-connectivity approach and an interoperable and hybrid data management environment.

EXPECTED IMPACT

PODIUM WILL:

- Provide increased road safety by providing real-time notifications about emergency cases;
- Improve the effectiveness of emergency services by sharing information about emergency incidents that require immediate access by public authorities;
- Improve traffic flow by providing real-time traffic data to the connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) and the rest of the vehicles;
- Lead to emissions reduction by shortening the time-to-destination for each driver;
- Minimize potential hazardous cases by increasing the Vulnerable Road User (VRU) detection rate.

Advancing technologies both in physical and digital infrastructures (PDI) to accelerate the wider deployment of CCAM solutions and make higher levels of automation an everyday reality for all.

Dr ANGELOS AMIDITIS (ICCS)
PoDIUM Coordinator

PROJECT INFO
Coordinated by ICCS (Institute of Communication & Computer Systems), the PoDIUM consortium comprises 24 partners from 8 European countries. The project runs from 1 October 2022 to 30 September 2025 and has a budget of €12.2M.

36 Months
24 Partners
3 Living Labs

CONSORTIUM

3 LIVING LABS, 5 USE CASES

- Germany
- Italy
- Spain

UC1: Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ujm
UC2: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance
UC3: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel
UC4: Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)
UC5: Responsive PDI enabling Vehicles and Road Users to Self-Manage in Real time for Mixed Traffic Optimisation on the Mediterranean Cross Border Corridor

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 23: PoDIUM leaflet

3.3. Posters

A poster presenting key information on PoDIUM has also been developed at M6 (March 2023). Other posters may also be produced if needed to highlight specific results and achievements or any other aspect of the project. They may be translated in different languages for participation in local events aimed at national audiences.

Figure 24: PoDIUM poster

3.4. Ad hoc printed promotional material

Similarly to digital promotional material, ad hoc printed material will also be created based on specific needs and purposes. For instance, stickers or flags with the project logo might be produced for the vehicles or the infrastructure used for the Living Labs demonstrations. This will help to further increase the visibility of the project.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable listed and explained the main communication tools developed as part of the PoDIUM project. These tools will be key for all dissemination or outreach activities of the project.

Various types of materials are used to promote the PoDIUM project, including a website, social media channels (X/Twitter and LinkedIn), a biannual newsletter, and videos. In addition to digital media, printed media will also be developed, such as a roll-up banner, flyers, and posters, to ensure maximum impact of the project's communication and dissemination activities.

All consortium partners have access to these communication tools and are encouraged to make use of them in all their dissemination activities. Partners should contribute to the website and social media channels of PoDIUM by regularly sharing news articles and any achievement of the project, ensuring a strong online presence for the project.

5. Annex

Annex 1

Content engagement ⓘ Time range: Feb 26, 2023 - Feb 26, 2024 Show: 20

Post title	Post type	Audience	Impressions	Views	Clicks	CTR	Reactions
You don't want to miss out on our 9 #HorizonEurope-funded research projects... Posted by Sevi Christoforou 2/22/2024 Not eligible to boost. Learn more	Repost	All followers	-	-	-	-	-
Transport Research Arena 2024 - PoDIUM Project Posted by Sevi Christoforou 2/19/2024 ⚡ Get more engagement Boost	Article	All followers	244	-	12	4.92%	13
Connecting Europe Days - PoDIUM Project Posted by Sevi Christoforou 2/16/2024 ⚡ Get more engagement Boost	Article	All followers	655	-	19	2.9%	12
Innovation overload on #RTR2024 Day 2! A whirlwind of electric excitement, exploring... Posted by Sevi Christoforou 2/7/2024 Not eligible to boost. Learn more	Image	All followers	-	-	-	-	-
🏠 We are in Brussels for the 2024 RTR Conference! During today's morning sessio... Posted by Sevi Christoforou 2/6/2024 Not eligible to boost. Learn more	Image	All followers	598	-	64	10.7%	34
🏠 The RTR Conference 2024 has officially begun and what an insightful day with som... Posted by Sevi Christoforou 2/6/2024 Not eligible to boost. Learn more	Image	All followers	-	-	-	-	-
Our funded projects at their mid-term are set to showcase their preliminary results. ✅... Posted by Sevi Christoforou 1/31/2024 Not eligible to boost. Learn more	Image	All followers	-	-	-	-	-
PoDIUM presented at Brno University of Technology - PoDIUM Project Posted by Sevi Christoforou 1/26/2024 ⚡ Get more engagement Boost	Article	All followers	377	-	6	1.59%	11
PoDIUM Newsletter #2 December 2023 Posted by Sevi Christoforou 1/25/2024 ⚡ Get more engagement Boost	Article	All followers	388	-	9	2.32%	11
🏠 PoDIUM Project's 3rd plenary meeting in Vienna! 📍 The 3rd Plenary Meeting of... Posted by Sevi Christoforou 1/18/2024	Image	All followers	1,752	-	348	19.86%	56

Figure 25: PoDIUM LinkedIn Content Engagement (Feb 23 – Feb 24)

<p> There is still some time to fill in our #survey and contribute to the #CCAM...</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>1/11/2024</p> <p>Not eligible to boost. Learn more</p>	<p>Repost</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>393</p> <p>-</p> <p>3</p> <p>0.76%</p> <p>9</p>
<p>Take part in our survey on market adoption! - PoDIUM Project</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>1/5/2024</p> <p> Get more engagement Boost</p>	<p>Article</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>365</p> <p>-</p> <p>9</p> <p>2.47%</p> <p>9</p>
<p>Season's greetings from the PoDIUM Project! We would like to wish everyone a wonderf...</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/22/2023</p> <p> Get more engagement Boost</p>	<p>Image</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>223</p> <p>-</p> <p>8</p> <p>3.59%</p> <p>14</p>
<p>Take part in our survey on market adoption! - PoDIUM Project</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/19/2023</p> <p> Get more engagement Boost</p>	<p>Article</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>602</p> <p>-</p> <p>26</p> <p>4.32%</p> <p>26</p>
<p>Managing data in the PoDIUM project: Meet AustriaTech - PoDIUM Project</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/18/2023</p> <p> Get more engagement Boost</p>	<p>Article</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>398</p> <p>-</p> <p>10</p> <p>2.51%</p> <p>21</p>
<p>Inside PoDIUM's Living Labs: Italy - PoDIUM Project</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/14/2023</p> <p> Get more engagement Boost</p>	<p>Article</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>258</p> <p>-</p> <p>4</p> <p>1.55%</p> <p>15</p>
<p>#RTR2024 Conference - CCAM 9 Horizon Europe funded projects - 1st results</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/14/2023</p> <p>Not eligible to boost. Learn more</p>	<p>Video</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p>
<p>The week started with the AWARD-H2020 Pan-European Workshop on...</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/11/2023</p> <p>Not eligible to boost. Learn more</p>	<p>Image</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>230</p> <p>-</p> <p>33</p> <p>14.35%</p> <p>12</p>
<p>PoDIUM hosted a successful first webinar on its architecture platform - PoDIUM Project</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/8/2023</p> <p> Get more engagement Boost</p>	<p>Article</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>231</p> <p>-</p> <p>12</p> <p>5.19%</p> <p>12</p>
<p>AWARD workshop #4: The AWARD Business Models Workshop</p> <p>Posted by Sevi Christoforou</p> <p>12/5/2023</p>	<p>Article</p> <p>All followers</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p>

Figure 26: Continued